

AI Chatbots for Educators: Transforming Online Learning in Higher Education

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Abstract. This study explores the experiences of pre- and in-service teachers using AI chatbots in Pedagogical Information and Communication Technology (ICTPED) Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), an online course designed to develop professional digital competence. Data was collected through an online questionnaire completed by 46 participants and follow-up interviews with eight students. The findings reveal that 52.2% of participants used chatbots to support their learning, while 47.8% did not. Participants primarily used chatbots to clarify course content, generate learning materials, and explore curriculum-related topics. Many students found chatbots to be valuable for developing conceptual understanding, providing instant feedback, and serving as brainstorming partners. Motivation for chatbot use included curiosity, ease of communication, and trust in the tool's feedback. Despite the reported benefits, some participants expressed concerns regarding the accuracy and reliability of chatbot-generated content. The study contributes to the growing body of research on AI in education by highlighting how chatbots can facilitate personalized learning experiences and self-regulated learning in online teacher education. Further research is needed to address challenges related to chatbot accuracy, over-reliance, and ethical considerations.

Keywords: AI Chatbots, Online Learning, Teacher Education

1 Introduction

The integration of chatbots in online education has emerged as a transformative approach, reshaping how learners and instructors interact with educational content [10]; [8]. By leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing, chatbots provide instant support, personalized feedback, and interactive learning experiences. They address key challenges such as limited instructor availability and the demand for scalable educational solutions [14]; [11]. As a result, AI chatbots have gained significant attention for their potential to enhance student engagement and self-directed learning in online courses.

In massive open online courses (MOOCs), where large numbers of participants require scalable and flexible support, chatbots have proven to be particularly beneficial. They assist learners in navigating course content, answering frequently asked questions, and

providing timely feedback, thereby enhancing engagement and motivation [10]; [8]. Chatbots have been widely adopted in various educational contexts, from primary education to higher education and professional training. In STEM fields, chatbots offer step-by-step guidance and scaffolding tailored to students' performance levels, aiding in problem-solving and conceptual understanding [5]; [6]. Similarly, in language learning, chatbots serve as conversational partners, promoting fluency, vocabulary acquisition, and self-directed learning [14]; [11].

Despite their potential benefits, challenges remain in the effective use of chatbots in online education. Concerns about the accuracy and reliability of chatbot-generated content, over-reliance by students, and inclusivity issues, such as accessibility for diverse learners, have been highlighted in previous research [1]; [13]. Additionally, ethical considerations related to data privacy and algorithmic biases require further exploration to ensure the responsible integration of chatbots in educational settings [1]; [17].

The present study aims to explore the use of AI chatbots in the ICTPED MOOC, an online course designed to develop professional digital competence (PDC) among pre- and in-service teachers. As one of Norway's longest running and most popular MOOCs, the ICTPED course provides an ideal setting to investigate how educators engage with chatbots to support their learning. Specifically, the study examines how participants used the chatbots, their motivation for doing so, and the types of support the chatbots provided in achieving their learning goals.

By analyzing data collected from 46 participants through questionnaire and follow-up interviews with a subset of students, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on chatbot use in professional development settings by addressing the following research question: *How did the pre- and in-service teachers engage in learning with chatbots in the ICTPED MOOC?* The findings aim to inform future improvements in chatbot design and implementation in teacher education and professional development programs, addressing both the opportunities and challenges of AI-driven learning support.

2 Students' Use of Chatbots in Online Courses: What Do We Know?

Chatbots have been widely adopted in diverse educational contexts, from primary education to higher education and professional training. In STEM fields, chatbots have been used to support problem-solving by providing step-by-step guidance and scaffolding strategies tailored to students' performance levels [5]; [6]. These tools have also been employed in language learning, where they simulate conversational practice to enhance fluency and vocabulary acquisition, supporting self-directed learning in both classroom and extracurricular settings [14]; [11].

The use of chatbots in online courses has shown significant benefits in fostering engagement and motivation. Studies demonstrate that immediate feedback provided by chatbots enhances learning outcomes especially in asynchronous learning environments where instructor interaction is limited [10]; [12]. Massive open online

courses (MOOCs), in particular, benefit from the scalability of chatbot technologies, which address learner queries and guide course navigation for thousands of participants simultaneously [8]; [11].

Chatbots have also been integrated into teacher education and professional development online courses. These courses, which often demand self-regulation and life-long learning skills, leverage chatbots to guide learners in setting goals, monitoring progress, and reflecting on their learning experiences [9]; [5]. For instance, the "Learning Buddy" chatbot was designed to assist participants in professional development courses with setting SMART goals, fostering structured learning approaches [9]. In collaborative settings, chatbots have been shown to facilitate discussions and peer feedback, creating opportunities for professional growth among educators. In flipped learning environments, chatbots support active learning by personalizing feedback and enabling real-time interaction, which is particularly beneficial in professional development courses where participants may have diverse skill levels and goals [2]; [9].

The benefits of chatbots in online courses are multifaceted. Chatbots enhance learning by providing instant, personalized feedback that reduces the need for instructor intervention [10]; [6]. They also foster motivation and engagement through gamification and adaptive learning pathways, which align with learners' individual goals and preferences [5]; [16]. Chatbots improve accessibility and scalability in online education, particularly in large-scale platforms like MOOCs. Their ability to function 24/7 ensures continuous support for learners, bridging gaps in instructor availability and accommodating diverse time zones [8]; [11]. Furthermore, chatbots in professional development settings enable educators to engage in self-paced learning while balancing their professional responsibilities [9]; [2].

Despite their potential, chatbots face several limitations that hinder their effectiveness. One key challenge is their limited contextual understanding, which can lead to inaccuracies or irrelevant responses, particularly in complex or domain-specific topics [1]; [13]. This limitation is especially problematic in professional development courses, where participants expect advanced, reliable guidance which current chatbot technologies may struggle to deliver [1]; [12]. Over-reliance on chatbots poses another concern, as it may reduce learners' critical thinking and problem-solving skills [5]; [10]. Additionally, inclusivity issues, such as linguistic barriers and limited accessibility for participants with diverse needs, remain significant concerns [11]; [5]. Ethical issues, such as data privacy and algorithmic biases, further complicate the integration of chatbots into educational systems (Adıgüzel et al., 2023; [17]. Additionally, inclusivity challenges persist, particularly for non-native speakers and participants with diverse needs, highlighting the importance of culturally responsive and linguistically adaptive chatbot designs [11]; [14].

In summary, the use of chatbots in online courses offers significant advantages, including personalized learning, enhanced engagement, and improved scalability. In teacher education and professional development, chatbots play a crucial role in fostering self-regulated learning, facilitating collaboration, and supporting lifelong learning goals. However, addressing challenges such as accuracy, over-reliance, inclusivity, and ethical concerns is essential for maximizing their potential. Therefore,

more research is needed on how chatbots may assist online learning specifically in professional development courses, incorporating ethical safeguards, and exploring learning behaviors and outcomes.

3 Method

3.1 Participants and setting

Data was collected through a questionnaire administered online to 228 pre- and in-service teachers enrolled in the ICTPED MOOC during spring semester 2024. In addition, we conducted interviews with 8 students who participated in the course.

The aim of the study was to explore the participants' learning experiences and students' use of subject-specific chatbots in the ICTPED MOOC. The questionnaire was designed to capture: (a) general information about the participants, (b) how they used the chatbots in the ICTPED MOOC and (c) how did students' interactions with chatbots contributed to achieving their learning outcomes.

The questionnaire consisted of 35 questions, employing a mix of formats, including a five-point Likert scale for quantitative measures and open-ended questions for qualitative insights. Tab. 1 shows the number of respondents to the questionnaire, their professional background and general evaluation of the ICTPED MOOC.

Table 1. The number of respondents to the questionnaire in 2023-24 and their general evaluation of the ICTPED MOOC

Years	Number of respondents	Male/female	Professional background	General evaluation of the ICTPED MOOC
2023-2024	46	Male = 15.7% Female = 84.3%	In-service teachers = 88% Pre-service teachers = 9% Other = 3%	Very little satisfied = 2.2% Little satisfied = 2.2% Somewhat satisfied = 6.5% Strongly satisfied = 65.2% Very strongly satisfied = 26.1%

3.2 ICTPED MOOC

The ICTPED MOOC, originally developed by researchers and development specialists at Østfold University College, was introduced in Norway in 2016. This MOOC is one of longest running and one of the most popular MOOCs in Norway. The course has an xMOOC structure, hosted on the Canvas platform, and aims to develop professional digital competence (PDC) among pre- and in-service teachers. Characterized by institutional focus, reliance on video resources, and automated assessments through quizzes, the ICTPED MOOC consists of eight modules completed over 20 weeks. Each module begins with an introduction that includes Introduction video and textual information (accessible directly on the page) and embedded research articles, enhanced

with relevant video content. Learners then engage in individual tasks and reflection questions, concluding each module with a multiple-choice quiz for summative assessment. Formative assessment is integrated in the modules in the form of small, strategically placed multiple-choice tests. Universal Design principles are embedded in the ICTPED MOOC, ensuring accessibility for all participants. Audio files are available on every webpage, and participants can also download each module in multiple formats, including audio files, podcasts, flat PDF files, or e-books. The complete list of modules in the ICTPED MOOC, along with the participants' progress plan, is provided in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Progress plan and the modules in the ICTPED MOOC.

Module number	Module name	Progress plan (week)
0	<i>Pre-course</i>	2
1	<i>ICT and learning</i>	3-4
2	<i>Digital studying techniques</i>	5-6
3	<i>Multimodal texts (examination module)</i>	7-9
4	<i>Cyber ethics</i>	10-11
5	<i>Classroom management in digital learning environments</i>	12-13
6	<i>Assessment for learning</i>	14-15
7	<i>AI in education</i>	16-17
8	<i>Flipped classroom (examination module)</i>	18-21

On successful completion of the ICTPEDMOOC, participants are awarded 15 European credit transfer and accumulation system (ECTS) credits.

In the final three modules, students were introduced to chatbots specifically trained on the curriculum for each module. These chatbots were created using OpenAI's technology for developing GPT models via the paid version of ChatGPT-4. To ensure accurate and subject-specific responses, the chatbots were trained using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technology, based on the curriculum content of the respective modules. The chatbots were practically integrated into the course by being prominently displayed on the main page of each module. Students were informed about the availability and functionality of the chatbots through three instructional videos. To access the chatbots, students were required to have their own subscription to the paid version of ChatGPT.

3.3 Data and Analysis

To address the research questions in the study, the following questions were included in the questionnaire administered to the participants in the ICTPED MOOC (1) Have you used GPT/chatbots in modules 6, 7 and 8? (Participants were to provide yes/no answers) (2) How do you assess the use of the GPT/chatbots? (Applied on a five-point Likert scale.) and (3) How did you use GPT/chatbots in modules 6, 7 and 8? (Participants were to provide detailed descriptive answers.) The dataset consisted of responses from 46

participants to questions Q1, Q2 and Q3. All responses were collected anonymously and on a voluntary basis. A mixed-methods approach [7] was used to analyze the data, combining both quantitative and qualitative evidence to examine participants' engagement with the chatbots. To explore participants' learning experiences with chatbots, eight interviews were analyzed thematically [3]; [8]. During the interviews the participants were asked the following questions: (4) How did you use the chatbots? (5) Why did you use the chatbots? and /6) What support did the chatbots provide to you? The data were imported into NVivo 12 and coded using an inductive thematic analysis approach, meaning that no predefined categories were applied [15]. A thorough thematic analysis was conducted by the research team to identify key themes, with each sentence being carefully examined for its relevance to the subject under study.

4 Findings

4.1 Analysis of the Questionnaire

Participants' learning experiences with GPT/chatbots were analyzed by first reviewing their responses to Q1: "Have you used GPT/chatbots in modules 6, 7, and 8?" The results indicate that **52.2%** of participants reported using GPT/chatbots in their learning, while **47.8%** did not. In response to Q2, "How do you assess the use of GPT/chatbots?", participants' feedback was distributed as follows: **0%** reported being *very little satisfied*, **0%** were *little satisfied*, **22.2%** were *somewhat satisfied*, **55.6%** were *strongly satisfied*, and **22.2%** were *very strongly satisfied*. The analysis of participants' responses to Q3, "How did you use GPT/chatbots in modules 6, 7, and 8?", is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Participants' Use of GPT/chatbots in ICTPED MOOC.

Theme	Explanation	Examples
Clarification and Understanding of Course Content	Many students used GPT/chatbots to verify their understanding of the material and clarify concepts they were uncertain about. This indicates that the tool served as a supplementary learning aid to reinforce comprehension.	<i>"When I have been uncertain or needed someone to discuss my understanding with, I have asked the AI if I was thinking correctly. Of course, with a pinch of salt."</i>
Content Creation and Task Assistance	Several students reported using GPT/chatbots to generate content such as assignments, quizzes, and educational materials, highlighting its role in facilitating creative and instructional processes.	<i>"It was interesting to use Chat GPT to write texts and become aware that the program is good at creating summaries, but that the information in the text can be very imprecise."</i>
Resource Gathering and	Students utilized GPT/chatbots to gather and summarize academic	<i>"Find relevant literature for the reflection video in module</i>

Creating Summaries	resources, such as relevant literature, videos, and articles, especially when they had limited time.	8."
Exploration and Experimentation	Several students expressed curiosity about GPT/chatbots, exploring its capabilities as part of their learning process, especially since the topic is current and relevant.	"I have mostly used GPT related to tasks/work in module 7, but I think it has been useful to explore the possibilities since this is a current topic (and it can be a good tool when used correctly)."

4.2 Analysis of the Interviews

In response to Q4: *How did you use the GPT/chatbots?* students reported using the chatbots to find relevant content in the curriculum, helping them navigate the material more effectively. Some students also used the chatbots to develop a deeper conceptual understanding, using the technology to clarify complex topics. In addition, several participants leveraged the chatbots to identify appropriate references from the curriculum, ensuring they were using the correct resources. The chatbots provided both brief and detailed answers, allowing students to choose the level of explanation they required. Finally, some students noted that tutorial videos generated by the chatbots were particularly helpful for enhancing their learning experience.

When asked Q5: *Why did you use the GPT/chatbots?* students provided a range of reasons reflecting their curiosity, positive experiences, and perceived benefits. Many students expressed a desire to try a new tool and explore its potential in their learning process. Several participants highlighted their positive experiences with the chatbot, which motivated them to continue using it. The chatbot's ease of communication was also a significant factor, as students found it to be an accessible and convenient resource. Additionally, they recognized the chatbot as a useful tool in online courses, helping them engage with the content more effectively. Trust in the chatbot's feedback was another important reason, with students relying on it to provide relevant and reliable information. Some students even described their experience as "a new world for students," emphasizing the chatbot's transformative potential in their educational journey.

When asked Q6: *What support did the chatbots provide?* students highlighted their role as a valuable communication and brainstorming partner in the online learning environment. The chatbots offered an interactive platform where students could engage in discussions, clarify doubts, and explore ideas more effectively. By serving as a responsive and readily available resource, the chatbots helped students think through complex topics, refine their understanding, and generate new ideas. Their ability to provide instant feedback and suggestions made them a useful tool for brainstorming,

allowing students to explore different perspectives and approaches within their coursework.

Overall, students found the chatbots to be a supportive companion in their learning process, enhancing their engagement and critical thinking in the online course.

5 Discussion

This study aimed to explore pre- and in-service teachers' learning experiences with AI chatbots in the ICTPED MOOC, focusing on their usage patterns, perceived benefits, and challenges. The findings align with previous research on the integration of chat-bots in online education, reinforcing their role in facilitating learning, enhancing engagement, and providing support across various educational contexts [5]; [6]; [14]; [11].

Chatbots as Learning Facilitators: Consistent with prior studies that highlight chatbots' potential to support problem-solving and personalized learning in STEM and language education [5]; [11]. Our findings demonstrate that participants used chat-bots primarily for clarification and understanding of course content. Many students reported leveraging the chatbots to verify their understanding, clarify complex concepts, and receive both brief and detailed explanations tailored to their needs. This reflects the adaptive and responsive nature of chatbots, similar to their use in STEM education, where they provide step-by-step guidance to enhance learning outcomes [6]. Additionally, chatbots were utilized as a tool for content creation and task assistance, with participants generating assignments, quizzes, and instructional materials. These findings echo research by [8], who emphasized the scalability of chatbots in MOOCs by assisting learners with course navigation and task completion. Participants also found chatbots beneficial for resource gathering and creating summaries, using them to locate relevant curriculum materials, academic references, and video content—an application that aligns with previous studies on chatbots' ability to facilitate self-directed learning [14].

Motivation and Engagement: The study findings highlight that participants were motivated to use chatbots for various reasons, including curiosity about the technology, positive past experiences, and the ease of communication offered by the tool. These findings resonate with research showing that chatbots enhance learner engagement by providing immediate feedback and promoting interactivity in online courses [10]; [12]. In particular, several participants described their experience as opening “a new world for students,” indicating a sense of empowerment and excitement, which aligns with previous studies emphasizing the motivational aspects of chatbots in online learning [9]. Moreover, the chatbot's perceived reliability and accessibility contributed to students' trust in the tool as a valuable resource for online learning. Similar to findings by [11], who noted that chatbots improve accessibility in large-scale learning environments, participants in our study recognized the chatbots as a convenient and efficient means of obtaining support, particularly when instructor availability was limited.

Support for Self-Regulated Learning: One of the key findings in this study is the chatbot's role as a communication and brainstorming partner. Participants found the chatbots to be valuable in exploring ideas, refining their understanding, and generating new insights. This aligns with previous research on chatbots' ability to foster self-regulated learning by guiding learners through goal setting, progress monitoring, and reflection [9]; [5]. The ICTPED MOOC participants used chatbots to engage in reflective learning processes, confirming prior findings that these tools can act as intelligent learning companions that scaffold the learning process [2].

Challenges and Limitations: Despite the reported benefits, several challenges were identified in the participants' responses. Some students noted concerns regarding the accuracy of chatbot-generated content, aligning with existing literature that highlights chatbots' limitations in providing domain-specific, contextually accurate responses [1]; [13]. This suggests the need for ongoing improvements in chatbot training to enhance content precision and minimize misleading or superficial explanations. Another key concern is the potential over-reliance on chatbots, which could impact students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as highlighted in previous studies [5]; [10]. Some participants expressed hesitation about using chatbots extensively, indicating a preference for traditional learning methods or instructor-led guidance. These findings suggest the importance of integrating chatbots as a supplementary rather than a primary learning tool to balance independent learning with expert guidance.

6 Implications and Concluding Reflections

The results of this study suggest several practical implications for the implementation of AI chatbots in teacher education and professional development. *First*, chatbot design should prioritize subject-specific accuracy and contextual understanding to better support professional development courses, particularly in complex educational domains. *Second*, instructional strategies should emphasize the complementary role of chatbots, encouraging students to critically evaluate chatbot responses rather than passively accepting them. *Finally*, accessibility and inclusivity considerations should be integrated into chatbot design to accommodate diverse learner needs, as suggested by prior research [11]; [14].

In summary, the findings of this study reinforce the potential of AI chatbots to enhance learning experiences in online teacher education and professional development programs. They provide valuable insights into how chatbots can support content understanding, self-regulated learning, and motivation, while also highlighting areas for improvement such as accuracy, over-reliance, and inclusivity.

Future research should explore the long-term impact of chatbot use on teaching practices and investigate how different chatbot features can be optimized to meet the evolving needs of pre- and in-service teachers. Further studies should also focus on ethical considerations, including data privacy and bias, to ensure responsible AI integration in educational settings [1]; [17].

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